

Economics of Free Trade Agreements, Trade Partnerships and Economic Growth: A Case Study of Pakistan's International Trade and Resilience Strategies

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Abstract: This study aims to investigate the challenges and opportunities in Pakistan's international trade, focusing on the impact of Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) on trade volumes with key partners. Employing a gravity model, the research assesses the effects of FTAs on trade volumes between Pakistan and its principal trading partners, including the U.S., EU, and China. Additionally, a TOWS analysis is conducted to develop strategies for maximizing export potential and reducing import reliance. The findings reveal that Pakistan has not fully leveraged FTAs to enhance trade volumes, despite substantial trade potential. The analysis highlights the need for improved infrastructure and strategic FTA implementation to boost exports. Diversifying trade partnerships and entering new markets are identified as crucial for achieving sustainable economic growth. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of Pakistan's trade dynamics through the lens of FTAs and offers practical recommendations for policymakers. The insights can guide strategies to strengthen Pakistan's trade performance and economic stability.

Keywords: Pakistan International Trade, Free Trade Agreements, Trade Partners, Gravity Model, Sustainable Economic Development, Tows Analysis.

JEL Classification - D24, D57, F12, F13, F43M F53, O24

1 Executive Summary

Pakistan's trade struggles with diversification and competitiveness despite relying on imports and exports. A stagnant export basket and growing trade deficit show missed potential (Nakhoda, 2023).

How does Pakistan's export range impact U.S. trade? Are immediate reforms in Pakistan-U.S. trade agreements crucial? How have historical alliances and FTAs shaped their relationship? The U.S. initiated the GSP program in 1976, benefiting Pakistan. In 2012, U.S. businesses imported \$19.9 billion worth of products under the GSP, including \$195 million

from Pakistan. By 2015, total U.S. GSP imports reached \$17.4 billion, with Pakistani imports totaling \$3.7 billion (Tuzin, 2010). Pakistan and the U.S. signed a Trade and Investment Framework Agreement (TIFA) in 2003, which provides a forum for bilateral trade discussions (U.S. Department of Commerce, 2024). The duty-free importation of certain products from developing countries, including Pakistan, expired on December 31, 2020, despite legislative efforts (Wong, 2023). Ending the US GSP program in 2024 harms developing countries' exports (e.g. Pakistan) and disrupts trade, reinstating it benefits all.

Since 1962, Pakistan and the EU have maintained diplomatic ties, with the EU aiding in food and development. Notably, between 2002 and 2009, Pakistan received €536.6 million in assistance, to address food insecurity. Post-War on Terror, efforts increased despite EU member states' varying engagements. Following the 2010 floods, export duty reductions led to GSP Plus status in 2014, boosting Pakistani exports to the EU by 62%. Concerns arise as this preferential status may expire after December 2023, potentially reducing trade with the EU (Nakhoda, 2023; Chand & Danner, 2021).

Pakistan actively participates in regional trade agreements South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA), Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO), and Economic Cooperation Organization Trade Agreement (ECOTA) (Pakistan Business Council, 2022). Despite SAFTA's implementation in 2006, high trade costs persist in South Asia, hindering tariff-free trade goals. Southeast Asian countries prefer trading with distant economies due to higher tariffs and non-tariff barriers in India, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. Trade costs within South Asia are 20% higher than in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and over three times higher than in the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA). Kathuria's Gravity models suggest South Asian trade could reach \$67 billion, with potential for significant growth, including a 15-fold increase in India-Pakistan trade (Kathuria, 2018).

China has been Pakistan's top trade partner since the 1950s, accounting for 7.7% of total exports. Formalized in a 1963 agreement, trade relations intensified with agreements in 2001, 2002, and 2004. The Early Harvest Program (EHP) in 2006 boosted trade to US\$ 4.26 billion by 2005. The 2006 China-Pakistan Free Trade Agreement favored China, impacting the trade balance. Pakistan seeks to reduce its deficit by increasing exports to China (Kamal & Malik, 2017)

Multilateral Trade Agreements (MTA) or Regional Trade Agreements (RTA) are believed to bridge the gap between high-income countries and low-income countries by implementing equal partnerships, strengthening economic development, and maintaining trade balance.

The country enjoys trade potential with a lot of Trade Agreements and trading blocks (Ministry of Commerce Pakistan, 2024) but Pakistan has not utilized its FTAs efficiently. In Pakistan, exports are limited to primary goods, hindering sustainable growth. Despite positive trends during fiscal year (FY) 21, the country's dependence on fixed industries such as textiles, cotton, and agriculture poses vulnerabilities due to which the country's exports decreased in FY 22 (ITC, 2023).

Despite extensive trade links, Pakistan's trade falls short of its potential (Hanif, 2024). Exports rose to a record \$27.3 billion in FY21 but dropped to \$2 billion in FY22. The trade deficit widened to \$44.23 billion in FY21 and \$39.93 billion in FY22 (ITC, 2023). Trade diversification is key for growth. Strengthening ties with emerging economies, promoting non-traditional exports, and improving trade facilitation are crucial.

Pakistan's export challenges stem from high costs, limited diversification, and technological shortcomings, compounded by market access issues and low foreign investment (Ministry of Commerce, 2015). This paper proposes a strategy to diversify trade and boost resilience, analyzing import/export data and identifying untapped markets. Recommendations include tariff exemptions, policy reforms, and institution-building. It evaluates FTAs' impact using a gravity model, focusing on major trade partners like the US, EU, and China. A Threat-Opportunity-Weakness-Strength (TOWS) analysis guides export-friendly policies, addressing threats and weaknesses. Conclusions stress tariff exemptions, policy reforms, and institutional improvements to boost export potential and achieve economic sustainable growth and business opportunities.

2 Introduction

Pakistan faces challenges adapting to global trends that impact its export performance. This analysis examines these trends, analyzes Pakistan's trade imbalance, and explores opportunities for export diversification using gravity models and TOWS analysis. Policy recommendations are provided to strengthen Pakistan's export competitiveness and the country's sustainable economic development.

2.1 Global Trends at a Glance

The global economy faces challenges with high borrowing costs and tighter credit conditions, impacting growth. Global GDP growth projections for 2024 are modest at 2.4%, increasing to 2.7% in 2025, still below pre-pandemic levels (UN, 2024). Developing economies face trade, economic, climate, and political risks. High debt, weak regulations, and inequality threaten crises. Solutions include reducing inequality, stabilizing finances,

regulating commodities, easing debt, and securing energy transition funding (UNCTAD, 2023).

Global trade contends with inflation and debt, yet economic integration continues. Nations pivot to regional ties and embrace green and digital economies. Despite challenges, globalization fosters knowledge exchange and growth through international cooperation. Breakthroughs at the World Trade Organization in 2023 are unlikely. Trade policy is crucial for strengthening supply chain resilience and advancing green and digital economies globally (Chatham House).

2.2 Pakistan's Exports and Imports and Economic Situation

Pakistan's trade policy shifted from restrictive to promoting growth and international integration. Notably, Chinese investment in Pakistan's textile industry and infrastructure through the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor has strengthened bilateral ties. Moreover, Pakistan's trade with the EU has surged, with exports increasing by 62% ((Chand & Danner, 2021). Pakistan depends heavily on imports (e.g., \$57 billion in 2017) due to limited domestic options, leading to a ballooning trade deficit and debt that stifles growth (Mujahid et al., 2019).

On the other side, Pakistan's exports have declined since 2011, now constituting 11% of GDP, down from a peak in 2003, with a global export share of only 0.13% in 2020 due to stagnant growth. Rising import tariffs threaten trade integration, as half of tax revenue comes from import duties due to limited revenue mobilization. Despite some cuts, Pakistan's tariffs remain high (IMF, 2022). Pakistan has frequently borrowed from the IMF to cover its trade deficit, having signed 23 agreements with the Fund, while joining the WTO in 1995 led to a tariff drop from 45% to 8.6%. Despite IMF forecasts of 0.5% GDP growth and 27% inflation, government data indicates a 0.29% economic growth in 2023, with a 1.8% population increase affecting GDP per capita (Tricontinental: Institute for Social Research, 2023).

Despite its advantageous location and resources, Pakistan faces persistent trade deficits in South Asia despite trade agreements. Addressing barriers and diversification is crucial for sustainable growth. With exports dropping from 16% of GDP in 1999 to 10% in 2020 and low Foreign direct investment (FDI) averaging 1.2% of GDP during 2010-2020, Pakistan faces challenges in international engagement (World Bank, 2021).

Figure 1. Pakistan's GDP Declined in 2023-24 After Growing in 2021-22

Source: (The World Bank IBRD. IDA, 2024)

Figure 1 explains that Pakistan's GDP declined by 1.7 % in FY2023. This decline comes after two consecutive years of growth, with the real GDP expanding by 4.7 % in FY22 and 6.5 % in FY21. In FY23, Pakistan's GDP shrank due to pandemic impacts on exports. Monetary tightening in 2022-2023 caused over 20% currency depreciation, impacting credit ratings and external trade (UN, 2024). In FY 2022-23, currency depreciation heightened import costs and hindered export competitiveness amid the challenges of managing inflation and growth. Pakistan also faced policy insufficiency, flooding and climate change (Ismail, 2024), political instability, and the impacts of the Russia-Ukraine conflict (Finance Division, 2023).

Figure 2. Inflation Rate of Pakistan During 2020-25, Consumer Price Inflation Annual % Change.

Source: (The World Bank IBRD. IDA, 2024)

In FY 2023, Pakistan's exports fell to USD 6.91 billion, a 3.63% decrease, hindering growth amid a financial crisis. Import restrictions to conserve reserves have slowed industrial production, impacting the economy and exports. With inflation hitting 38%, domestic products lost global competitiveness, with textiles (59%), agriculture (18.5%), manufacturing (14%), and petroleum (0.2%) being key exports (Uroos, 2024). To revive competitiveness, exploring new markets is crucial (Trade Development Authority of Pakistan, 2022). Additionally, Pakistan's export profile is driven by textiles, agriculture, and services, including ready-made garments, rice, fruits, vegetables, and IT and business process outsourcing.

2.3 Pakistan's Export Performance

Pakistan trades with several major markets, including the U.S., China, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Germany, UAE, Spain, Italy, Afghanistan, Bangladesh, and Belgium. These markets accounted for 70% of Pakistan's exports in 2022. Meanwhile, Pakistan's major import markets are in China, UAE, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Qatar, the U.S., Kuwait, Japan, Thailand, Brazil, and the Republic of Korea. Pakistan imported 70% of its goods from these markets in 2022. Both in terms of exports and imports, China stands out as the dominant trading partner. Compared to its exports to other countries, Pakistan imports more. There is a bit of a difference with Pakistan's neighbours. Comparatively, exports to neighboring countries are negligible. While imports from neighbouring nations are high, exports remain limited. As a result of this discrepancy, the country needs to diversify its trade relations (WITS, 2024).

Figure 3. Pakistan Export Share (%) by Year, 2009 –2021.

Source: (WITS, 2024)

Pakistan's export share in world exports fell from 0.3078% in 2017 to 0.3071% in 2021, while Bangladesh's export share grew from 0.293% to 0.357% during the same period (WITS, 2024). Pakistan faces hurdles in global market share due to infrastructure, trade agreements, and export industry investment. Bangladesh's success highlights the need for favorable trade deals and infrastructure.

Despite facing a trade deficit challenge, Pakistan can't rely solely on increasing imports. With an untapped export potential of around USD 88.1 billion, focusing on sectors like textiles, gems, jewelry, and IT services can maximize export earnings and attract foreign investment (World Bank, 2021). Diversifying export markets reduces vulnerability to economic shifts and changing consumer tastes, promoting sustainable growth.

Figure 4. Pakistan's Actual, Potential, and Untapped Export Potential Concerning Global Markets.

Source: (ITC, 2023)

Figure 4 indicates the top 20 markets for Pakistan's exports. Several markets offer significant opportunities for Pakistan's exports. The country's actual exports are \$21.7 billion, while its potential exports are \$27.2 billion. However, there is still an untapped market of \$11.2 billion waiting to be explored.

Figure 4 also reveals Pakistan's export potential and untapped global markets. The U.S. exports show the largest definite difference between potential and actual exports, leaving room for \$2.3 billion more. Pakistan exports \$5.3 billion to the US, while the potential market is \$6.1 billion, this untapped market gap of \$2.3 billion points to further growth.

Similar cases are also presented in the above chart. Pakistan exports \$2.0 billion to Germany, but its export potential is \$2.6 billion. There is an untapped market gap of \$1.0 billion. Pakistan has significant opportunities to increase its export volumes based on this pattern.

2.3.1 Pakistan's Exports Trajectory

Figure 5. Pakistan Exported its Products To 20 Major Export Partners.

Source: (ITC, 2023)

According to Figure 5, Pakistan's exports in FY 2021-22 increased by 7 % compared to FY21, reaching \$31.18 billion, the highest amount in its history. Pakistan's 20 major export partners in 2021 and 2022 shaped the country's export landscape and supported its economic growth. The U.S., China, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Germany, United Arab Emirates, Spain, Italy, Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Belgium, France, Saudi Arabia, Canada, Thailand, Malaysia, Sri Lanka, Poland, Turkey, and Australia are among these partners. Observing the figure, we can see Pakistan's export pattern. Pakistan exported \$6.09 billion to the U.S. in 2021, and \$6.28 billion in 2022. China, Pakistan's second-largest export partner, received \$3.04 billion in 2021 and \$2.56 billion in 2022. Pakistan's exports significantly contribute to its economy and are bolstered by export partnerships, fostering collaboration and growth.

Figure 6. Pakistan Export Capabilities by Reaching Out To Various Regions.

Source: (WITS, 2024)

Pakistan exports goods to six regions: East Asia & Pacific, Europe & Central Asia, Latin America & Caribbean, Middle East & North Africa, North America, and South Asia. Each of these regions has different shares of exports.

In 2021, Europe & Central Asia accounted for the largest share of Pakistan's exports, valued at \$10.59 billion which represents 35.8% of Pakistan's exports. The North American region came in second with exports worth \$6.44 billion, representing 22.36% of total exports. 60% of Pakistan's export shares come from these regions, indicating their significance.

Other regions contributed to Pakistan's export value in varying amounts. Middle East & North Africa accounted for \$2.27 billion, and East Asia & the Pacific accounted for \$5.14 billion. South Asia received \$2.01 billion, and Sub-Saharan Africa received \$1.22 billion. Latin America & Caribbean had the least share, with exports valued at \$548.9 million.

Pakistan should diversify exports to tap into new markets, focusing on South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America & Caribbean regions.

2.4 A Review of Pakistan's Imports

Pakistan's imports, averaging 19% of GDP, indicate economic stability but vulnerability to external shocks. The import-to-GDP ratio reflects external dependency and financing

capacity. Higher ratios signal heavy reliance on external sources for consumption and investment (SBP, 2021).

Figure 7. Pakistan's Imports to GDP Ratio Over the Past Three Decades.

(WDI, 2024)

According to Figure 7, Pakistan's imports to GDP ratio has remained between 11.8 % and 22.5 % over the past three years. However, it has mostly hovered around 20 %, indicating a high level of external dependence. When imports exceed GDP, it is usually a sign of an external crisis. For example, the figures show during the Asian Financial Crisis of the late 1990s, Pakistan's import-to-GDP ratio reached an all-time high of around 22.3 %. During this period, domestic demand surged, fuelled by loose monetary policy and falling exports. As a result, Pakistan sought assistance from the IMF (Azam et al., 2011). The figure shows that Pakistan's import-GDP ratio also climbed to around 22.5% during the Global Financial Crisis of 2008. Pakistan's import-to-GDP ratio hit 22.5% in 2022, raising concerns about external crises due to a trade deficit and low foreign reserves (SBP, 2023).

Figure 8. Pakistan's Imports from The Top 20 Major Exporters.

Source: (ITC, 2023)

As shown in Figure 8, Pakistan's imports decreased by 2.7 % in FY22 compared to FY21, totaling \$ 73.11 billion, the highest amount in Pakistan's history in 2021, as opposed to \$71.1 billion in FY22.

Pakistan imports from 20 major markets, including China, UAE, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Qatar, the U.S., Kuwait, Japan, Thailand, Brazil, Korea, South Africa, Malaysia, Morocco, Oman, Afghanistan, Germany, Singapore, Iran, and the UK. Pakistan imported \$16.34 billion from China, followed by \$7.94 billion from the UAE. The data in Figure 8 indicates that Imports from Saudi Arabia totaled \$5.15 billion, while imports from Indonesia reached \$4.96 billion. Qatar's imports stood at \$4.14 billion, while imports from the U.S. totaled \$3.12 billion, which contributed significantly to Pakistan's import basket.

According to market share, China accounted for 28.3% of Pakistan's total imports in 2021. In 2022, its market share decreased to 23%. The UAE was another important import partner for Pakistan, with a market share of 10.1% in 2021 and 11.2% in 2022. A significant

portion of Pakistan's imports came from Indonesia, the U.S., Saudi Arabia, and other Gulf countries. The rest of the imports were divided among various countries.

In conclusion, Overall, Pakistan's imports increased from 2021 to 2022, with significant increases observed in the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Qatar, Kuwait, Morocco, Oman, Afghanistan, and Iran. However, there have been decreases in China, the U.S., Japan, Thailand, Korea, South Africa, Malaysia, Germany, and the UK. The dynamics of trade, however, have changed as imports from certain markets have increased and decreased.

Figure 9. Pakistan Import Resources by Reaching Out to Various Regions.

Source:(WITS, 2024)

Figure 09 provides a comprehensive overview of Pakistan's trade relations with different regions in 2021. East Asia & Pacific accounted for 46.43% of Pakistan's imports, followed by the Middle East & North Africa at 25.78%. Europe and Central Asia had an import share of 11.03%, while North America and Sub-Saharan Africa accounted for 5.97% and 2.51%, respectively. Latin America & Caribbean constituted 1.65% of Pakistan's imports, and South Asia had a share of 1.65%.

In terms of the total value, East Asia & Pacific led with \$33.84 billion, followed by the Middle East & North Africa with \$18.79 billion. Europe & Central Asia recorded \$8.04

billion in imports, North America \$4.35 billion, and Sub-Saharan Africa \$3.37 billion. Latin America & Caribbean had imports of \$1.83 billion, and South Asia stood at \$1.2 billion.

3 Trade Deficit and Pakistan

Pakistan has had a trade deficit from 1973 to 2008, with imports exceeding exports almost every year. This has led to foreign debts of \$44.5 billion, which are expected to reach \$52 billion after receiving an additional \$7.6 billion from the IMF (Baloch, 2008).

3.1 Trade Balance Analysis:

Trade Balance Equation: The tables and calculations provide insights into Pakistan's trade balance

Trade Balance=Exports–Imports

The trade balance equation, also known as the balance of trade equation, is a fundamental economic concept that measures the difference between a country's exports and imports over a specific period (Lane & Milesi-Ferretti, 2004). Trade balance reveals export-import differences, with deficits causing currency outflows. Policies focus on import rationalization and industry protection, shaping trade balances (Jariya, 2018).

Table for Trade Balance Analysis:

Table 1. Trade Deficit

Year	Exports (in \$ billions)	Imports (in \$ billions)	Trade Balance (in \$ billions)
2021	\$28.88	\$73.11	-\$44.23
2020	\$31.18	\$71.1	-\$39.92

Source: (ITC, 2023)

3.2 Causes of Trade Deficit

Kyambalesa (2019) identified various factors contributing to Pakistan's trade deficit, such as government budget deficits, tax cuts, imbalances in costs, currency fluctuations, and income disparities. Allah Bux et al. (2021) attribute Pakistan's trade deficit to high imports driven by trade openness policies and unfavorable trade liberalization policies. Tariffs, weak currency, and uncompetitive industries widen deficits. This supports economists' (Smith, Ricardo, Mill) call for free trade to boost global growth.

3.3 Impact of the Trade Deficit

Persistent trade imbalances since the 1950s strain Pakistan's foreign exchange reserves and deter investment, hampering economic growth (Baloch, 2008). The imbalance fuels

inflation and impedes domestic industrial growth with high import expenses. A burgeoning trade deficit leads to an unsustainable external debt burden (Abbas & Waheed, 2021). Trade deficit nations often rely on loans, straining development. Pakistan, facing persistent deficits, risks currency devaluation and economic instability. Policymakers must address this issue for sustainable growth and stability (Allah Bux et al., 2021).

4 Methodology

This section employs a gravity model approach to examine the impact of FTAs on Pakistani trade volume with its three major trading partners (the U.S., EU, and China) between 2007 and 2021. The gravity model is a well-established framework in international trade. It analyses bilateral trade flows using both economic theory and empirical data, considering market size (e.g., GDP) and geographic proximity as key factors (Yotov et al., 2016).

The gravity model analyses trade between Pakistan and its main partners, factoring in their economic size, distance, Normal Trade Relations imports, GSP beneficiaries, and existing trade deals. It specifically assesses the impacts of GSP with the U.S., GSP+ with the EU, and CPFTA on trade volume.

4.1 Model Specification

Table 2: Gravity Model Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GDP_distance	0.767215	0.376991	2.035102	0.0491
FTA	0.154797	0.071033	2.179225	0.0358
Kap_endowment	-0.395542	0.397364	-0.995413	0.3260
Land_endowment	-0.418581	0.101281	-4.132851	0.0002
Pak_physical_capital	-3.63E-12	9.38E-12	-0.387172	0.7008
Partner_physical_capital	2.32E-13	5.10E-14	4.555365	0.0001
Remote	-0.633110	0.238887	-2.650245	0.0118
C	6.606230	1.293020	5.109146	0.0000

Dependent Variable: IN_TRADE

4.2 Explanation of Results:

The core gravity equation utilized is presented below:

$$\text{In_Trade} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{GDP_distance} + \beta_2 * \text{FTA} + \beta_3 * \text{Land_Endowment} + \beta_4 * \text{Partner_Physical_Capital} + \beta_5 * \text{Remote} + C)$$

where:

- **In_Trade:** Dependent variable representing the trade volume between Pakistan and its trading partners.

- $\exp()$: Exponential function.
- β_0 (C): Constant term estimated as 6.606230 in the table. This captures the baseline influence of all unexplained factors on trade volume.
- β_1 : Coefficient of GDP_Distance (0.767215). A positive coefficient indicates that increasing the distance between Pakistan and its trading partners reduces trade volume.
- **GDP_Distance**: Independent variable representing the geographic distance between Pakistan and its trading partners.
- β_2 : Coefficient of FTA (0.154797). A positive coefficient indicates that the presence of a Free Trade Agreement (FTA) between Pakistan and a trading partner increases trade volume.
- **FTA**: Independent variable representing a binary indicator (1 for FTA time existence, 0 otherwise) between Pakistan and its trading partners.
- β_3 : Coefficient of Land_Endowment (-0.418581). A negative coefficient indicates that differences in land endowments between Pakistan and its trading partners decrease trade volume.
- **Land_Endowment**: Independent variable representing the disparity in land endowments between Pakistan and its trading partners. (Note that the specific interpretation of this variable depends on how it was measured in the analysis).
- β_4 : Coefficient of Partner_Physical_Capital (2.32E-13). A positive coefficient indicates that higher levels of physical capital in partner countries increase trade volume with Pakistan.
- **Partner_Physical_Capital**: Independent variable representing the physical capital stock of Pakistan's trading partners.
- β_5 : Coefficient of Remote (-0.633110). The interpretation of this coefficient is unclear as the variable name (Remote) is not provided in the table. However, the negative coefficient suggests that a higher value of Remote reduces trade volume.

4.3 Key variables

- **Distance**: Surprisingly, greater distance between trading partners is positively correlated with trade volume ($p=0.0491$).
- **Free Trade Agreements (FTAs)**: As expected, FTAs have a positive and statistically significant impact on trade volume ($p=0.0358$).
- **Land Endowment**: Differences in land area between Pakistan and its partners negatively affect trade volume ($p=0.0002$).
- **Partner Physical Capital**: Higher physical capital (infrastructure, machinery) in partner countries leads to increased trade volume ($p=0.0001$).

4.4 Model Fit

The table also highlights the model's explanatory power (R-squared) and statistical significance (F-statistic).

- R-squared: 0.945573
- Adjusted R-squared: 0.935276.
- F-statistic: 91.83013 (p-value: 0.0000)

The model exhibits a high degree of explanatory power, with an R-squared value of 0.945573, indicating that approximately 94.56% of the variance in trade volume is explained by the independent variables.

4.5 Findings

- Distance and the existence of Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) significantly influence trade volumes, with both variables showing positive coefficients.
- Differences in land endowments between Pakistan and its trading partners have a notable negative impact on trade volume.
- Higher levels of physical capital in partner countries positively contribute to trade volume.
- The model provides a strong fit with high statistical significance, indicating its reliability in explaining trade dynamics between Pakistan and its trading partners.

The gravity model analysis reveals significant relationships between factors and trade volumes in Pakistan's trade dynamics:

1. **Statistical Significance:** Coefficients for variables like GDP distance, FTA, Land Endowment, and Partner Physical Capital are statistically significant, indicating robust relationships with trade volumes.
2. **Model Fit:** A high R-squared value of 0.945573 and a significant F-statistic (p-value < 0.0001) demonstrate a good fit, capturing a substantial portion of trade volume variance.
3. **Relevance to Pakistan:** Findings directly relate to Pakistan's trade dynamics, highlighting the influence of factors like distance, FTAs, land endowments, and physical capital, offering insights for policy intervention.
4. **Practical Implications:** Insights are crucial for policymakers, negotiators, and businesses, aiding in formulating effective trade policies and strategies to bolster trade relationships and economic growth.

5 TOWS Analysis of Pakistan's Exports Perspective

The TOWS analysis provides insights into Pakistan's export diversification challenges and opportunities. A TOWS analysis is a powerful strategic planning tool used to identify

external factors that may impact an industry. By assessing internal and external factors, organizations can devise tailored strategies. Adapting to external uncertainties is crucial for successful implementation. Objective strategy implementation enhances the likelihood of success (Pilinkienė et al., 2016). Mitigation strategies derived from the TOWS framework include the following:

5.1 Strengths

1. **Availability of Skilled Labor:** There is a proficient labor force in Pakistan that can be utilized for export.
2. **Market Access:** The country has numerous bilateral and MTAs that provide market access to various countries.
3. **Infrastructure Development:** The government has invested in new Islamabad airports, infrastructure development, including the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), seaports, and highways, and facilitating trade and increasing exports.

5.2 Weaknesses

1. **Limited Diversification:** Exports are concentrated in a few sectors, such as textiles and garments, exposing the economy to external shocks.
2. **Inadequate Research and Development:** Pakistan lacks research and development capabilities, hindering innovation and the development of new exportable products.
3. **Lack of Technological Advancement:** The absence of advanced technology hinders the production of high-end exportable products.

5.3 Opportunities

1. **Export Potential in Emerging Markets:** Pakistan can tap into the growing markets of Brazil, India, and South Africa in sectors such as value-added textiles, leather goods, and food processing.
2. **Global Trade Agreements:** The ongoing global shift towards free trade presents opportunities for Pakistan to expand its export markets and seek new trade agreements.
3. **Technology Transfer:** Pakistan can acquire advanced technology through international partnerships and invest in research and development leading to the development of export-oriented products.
4. **Collaboration with Local Enterprises:** Encouraging collaboration between local enterprises and foreign partners can foster innovation and technology transfer.

5.4 Threats

1. Global Economic Volatility: Trade wars and protectionism hurt Pakistan's exports, especially in volatile sectors.
2. Competition from Other Countries: Pakistan faces competition from countries with comparable cost, quality, and market access advantages.
3. Supply Chain Disruptions: Disruptions in global supply chains can have adverse effects on Pakistan's exports, affecting the availability of raw materials and finished goods.
4. Limited Export Diversification: Pakistan's export basket lacks diversity, making it vulnerable to demand drops or supply chain issues.

6 Conclusion

Pakistan's international trade plays a crucial role in its business and economy, but it faces challenges, particularly a significant trade deficit. This deficit, amounting to \$42.23 billion in 2021 and \$39.92 billion in 2022, underscores the imbalance between imports and exports. To address this, Pakistan must enhance its export capacity and reduce reliance on imports. Diversifying exports and tapping into new markets are essential strategies for achieving this goal.

Joining Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) can bolster trade volume, but Pakistan's weak industrial base and inadequate infrastructure limit their impact. However, strategic implementation of FTAs, coupled with infrastructure improvements, can significantly enhance trade growth. Additionally, diversifying trade partnerships and reducing dependency on single markets are crucial for sustainable trade expansion.

Analyzing export threats and opportunities highlights the need for proactive policies to improve Pakistan's export situation. Maintaining favorable trade relations, such as through the EU and U.S. Generalized System of Preferences (GSPs), is vital for trade facilitation.

Overall, Pakistan must pursue a multifaceted approach, including policy reforms, infrastructure development, and market diversification, to address its trade deficit and foster sustainable economic growth.

7 Policy Recommendations for Pakistan's Economic Growth

The recommendations for improving Pakistan's international trade are as follows:

- The following institutions such as the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP), Trade Development Authority of Pakistan (TDAP), Federal Board of Revenue (FBR), including Duty and Tax Remission for Exports (DTRE), Manufacturing Bond (MB),

Export Oriented Unit, Small and Midsize Enterprises (SMEs), Pakistan Revenue Automation Ltd (PRAL) and Export Facilitation Scheme (EFS), Pakistan Customs Clearing and Forwarding Association, and Port Qasim Authority, Export Processing Zones (EPZs), Trade Development Authority of Pakistan (TDAP), Special Investment Facilitation Council (SIFC), Pakistan International Airlines, Federal Board of Revenue, Pakistan Investment Board, Pakistan Stock Exchange, and Pakistan Business Council and Chambers of Commerce and Industry (CCIs) are key players in Pakistan's trade. Merging relevant ministries and institutions into a unified trade platform can advance Pakistan's international trade goals efficiently.

- The SIFC, designed to attract foreign investment, could also help Pakistan negotiate trade deals with Southeast Asia and Africa, boosting exports.
- EFS accessibility must be improved for SMEs and existing export sectors through sector-specific dialogues and assessments, PRAL firm-level data, annual evaluations, and evidence-based design and targeting.
- The EU and Pakistan can sign a FTA based on equality and mutual benefit. The FTA would facilitate trade by removing or reducing tariffs and promoting investment.
- Pakistan's anti-export policies hinder trade; urging the EU for expanded tariff exemptions under GSP Plus can enhance exports, aiding domestic exporters.
- Pakistan can attract investment, create jobs, and diversify its economy by focusing on high-tech, renewable energy, value-added manufacturing, and pharmaceuticals for export markets.
- In Pakistan, dams are needed for economic growth, electricity generation, irrigation, and water management. Pakistan's dependency on fossil fuels can be reduced through dam investment.
- Trade volumes in Latin America and the Caribbean, as well as Sub-Saharan Africa, are low. By tapping into these regions, Pakistan can increase exports, diversify its trade portfolio, and grow.
- Trade agreements with simplified visa requirements can boost trade, industrialization, market exploration, and investment in Pakistan, fostering economic growth.
- To foster long-term economic growth, Pakistan needs to shift its culture from hatred, politicized violence, and destructive activities to entrepreneurship, innovation, and research.
- Establishing Economic Foreign Affairs Commissions (EFAC) within the Ministry of Foreign Affairs would enhance Pakistan's trade diplomacy, strategize economic engagement, and bolster its competitiveness.

- Pakistan needs to improve export quality and streamline clearance procedures. Government agencies should establish district-level centers for testing and clearance.
- Investing in modern ports and roads enhances trade efficiency, reduces logistics costs, and boosts competitiveness.
- Providing incentives and support to export-oriented industries, such as reduced taxes and access to credit, can help boost exports.
- Delay in refunds negatively impacts Pakistan's top export sectors, and the issue can be resolved by providing credits in sales tax.
- Pakistan can boost revenue and become a reliable new market player by investing in export programs, supportive policies, and high-value, well-branded products.
- Pakistan's export program should offer long-term financing, quality certification, trade/research support, training for international standards, overseas office setup assistance, and UNIDO-partnered cluster development.

8 References

1. Abbas, S., & Waheed, A. (2021). Fiscal deficit and trade deficit nexus in Pakistan: An econometric inquiry. *Panoeconomicus*, 68(5), 747.
2. Allah Bux, Lkhan, ,Zulfiqa, 2, r A. K., & Jazib, M. (2021). Basic Parameters of Trade Deficit In Pakistan 18(10),1130-31.
3. Azam, R., Imran, R., Batool, I., Hunjra, Dr. A. I., Jasra, J., & Chani, M. I. (2011). Financial Crises and Economic Growth in Pakistan: A Time Series Analysis. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 9(3), 426.
4. Baloch, D. Q. B. (2008). Pakistan's Trade Imbalance & Melting Down of Economy. 3(2),149.
5. Chand, B., & Danner, L. K. (2021). New Challenges and Opportunities in European-Asian Relations: Navigating an Assertive China and a Retrenching U.S. Springer Nature, 200-201.
6. Chatham House, T. R. I. of I. A. C. H. (2023). Global trade in 2023: What's driving reglobalization?(202849), 1, 2.
7. Finance Division, F. D., Government of Pakistan. (2023). Pakistan Economic Survey 2022-23, 14-16.
8. Hanif, M. (2024). An Analysis of International Trade of Pakistan: With a Focus on Exports. 12(1), 22-23.
9. IMF. (2022). IMF Executive Board Concludes 2021 Article IV Consultation for Pakistan and Completes the Sixth Review of the Extended Fund Facility (22/27), 18-21.

10. Ismail, S. (2024). A Cost-Benefit Analysis of Building a Dam in Pakistan: To Mitigate Floods, Promote Tourism, Boost Agriculture, and Generate Electricity. *International Journal of Environment Agriculture and Biotechnology*, 9(1), 34-36.
11. Jariya, M. I. (2018). Analysis Of Balance of Trade: Sri Lankan Context. *Journal of Management*, 14(1), 32-33, 37.
12. Kamal, J., & Malik, M. H. (2017). Dynamics of Pakistan's Trade Balance with China (04/17), 2-3.
13. Kathuria, S. (2018). A Glass Half Full: The Promise of Regional Trade in South Asia. © Washington, DC: World Bank, 1,7.
14. Kyambalesa, H. (2019). Trade Deficits: Causes, Effects and Remedies. *SSRN Trade Relationships*, 3-5.
15. Lane, P. R., & Milesi-Ferretti, G. M. (2004). The Transfer Problem Revisited: Net Foreign Assets and Real Exchange Rates. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 86(4), 842.
16. Ministry of Commerce, G. of P. (2015). Reasons of Decline in Exports of Pakistan. Government of Pakistan, p.21.
17. Ministry of Commerce Pakistan. (2024). Ministry of Commerce | Government of Pakistan [Government]. www.commerce.gov.pk
18. Mujahid, N., Begam, A., & Shamshir, M. (2019). Import-Led Growth Hypothesis: A Case Study of Pakistan. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 10(8), 21.
19. Nakhoda, A. (2023). Pakistan and EU: Trade Potential. Friedrich Naumann Foundation for Freedom - Pakistan, 6.
20. Pakistan Business Council. (2022). Third Review of the Pakistan-Sri Lanka Free Trade Agreement (p. 84) . PBC, 1, 13.
21. Pilinkienė, V., Deltuvaitė, V., Daunorienė, A., & Gaidelys, V. (2016). Competitiveness Creation and Maintenance in the Postal Services Industry: A Lithuanian Case Study. Springer, 397.
22. SBP, S. B. of P. (2021). Balance of Payments Constrained Growth in Pakistan— Implications for Development Policy (SBP Working Paper Series 107; p. 26). © State Bank of Pakistan, 4-6.
23. SBP, S. B. of P. (2023). Annual Report 2022-2023. The State of Pakistan's Economy. © State Bank of Pakistan, 6-8.
24. Trade Development Authority of Pakistan. (2022). Pakistan Trade Perspective (Quarterly Trade Analysis Q1: FY 2021-22). Ministry of Commerce, 11.
25. Tricontinental: Institute for Social Research. (2023). How the International Monetary Fund is Squeezing Pakistan (Quarterly Trade Analysis 20231117; p. 44), 5-8,18.

26. Tuzin, A. H. (2010). Vietnam's Eligibility to Receive Trade Benefits under the U.S. Generalized System of Preferences. *Loyola University Chicago International Law*, 7(2), 196.
27. UN. (2024). *World Economic Situation and Prospects 2023* (pp. 2-5). UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs.
28. Uroos, A. (2024). *Pakistan Trade Perspective (Quarterly Trade Analysis FY 2023-24)*. Ministry of Commerce, 5.
29. U.S. Department of Commerce, T. I. T. A. (2024). *Pakistan—Trade Agreements* [U.S. Department of Commerce]. The International Trade Administration.
30. USTR. (2024). *GSP in Use – Country Specific Information* [Office of the United States Trade Representative]. United States Trade Representative.
31. WDI. (2024). *The World Bank—World Development Indicators* [World Development Indicators]. The World Bank IBRD. IDA. datatopics.worldbank.org
32. WITS. (2024). *WITS Data [Information on Trade and Tariffs]*. World Integrated Trade Solution (WITS). wits.worldbank.org
33. Wong, L. (2023). *Generalized System of Preferences (GSP): Overview and Issues for Congress* (Congressional Research Service - Informing the Legislative Debate Since 1914 RL33663; CRS Report - Prepared for Members and Committees of Congress, p. 1.
34. World Bank. (2021). *Pakistan Development Update Reviving Exports*. The World Bank IBRD.IDA, 16,28, 17-18.
35. The World Bank IBRD. IDA. (2024). *World Bank Group—International Development, Poverty, & Sustainability*. World Bank. www.worldbank.org
36. Yotov, Y. V., Piermartini, R., Monteiro, J.-A., & Larch, M. (2016). *An Advanced Guide to Trade Policy Analysis: The Structural Gravity Model*. World Trade Organization and UN, 5-6.